
Functional outcomes of proximal tibial fractures treated by open reduction and internal fixation: A hospital based prospective study

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Abstract:

Objectives: The primary objective of the present study was to determine the functional outcome (using modified Rasmussen clinical scores) of proximal tibial fractures treated by open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) using three column concept with a minimum follow up period of six months. We also determined the complications of proximal tibial fracture fixation. **Methods:** This was a prospective study conducted among patients (15-60 years of age, of both gender) with proximal tibia fractures treated using three column concept conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics of a tertiary healthcare hospital in south India between March 2018 and February 2020. **Results:** The present study included a total of 60 patients with a mean (SD) age of 38.72 years (3.21). The proportion of males and females were 81.7% and 18.3% respectively. Road traffic accidents (RTA) were the most common mode of injury, followed by accidental fall from height (13.3%). Nearly one in four patients (23.3%) had one column involvement, 46.7% had two and 30.0% had three column involvement. In the present study, 6.7% patients had screw pullout, 10.0% had knee stiffness, and 10.0% had wound site infection. The mean (SD) duration of follow up was 12.5 months. Based on Rasmussen's clinical scores, 20.0% patients had excellent, 63.3% had good, and 16.7% had fair scores. Importantly, none of the patients included in the present study had poor scores. The patients with one column involvement had good to excellent outcomes, in comparison with patients having two or three column involvement having fair outcomes (reduced scores) ($p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Patients with one-column involvement (either medial or lateral) tended to achieve better functional outcomes than those with two or three columns involved. This distinction was statistically significant, emphasizing the impact of fracture complexity on patient recovery.

Keywords: Proximal tibia fractures, Rasmussen's clinical scores, Functional outcomes, India.

Introduction

Proximal tibia fractures are one of the commonest intraarticular fractures.(1) The epidemiology of proximal tibial fractures is changing.(2, 3) This is related to changing lifestyles, vehicular movement as well as an ageing society. Our understanding of the fracture patterns has changed with the increased use of three-dimensional computed tomography (CT) scan and the methods of fixation have altered accordingly.(4) This has given rise to newer classifications with more emphasis on the posterior part of the tibial plateau.(5, 6) Open fractures and other associated injuries are common in this fracture group and have important prognostic significance.

The incidence of proximal tibial fractures is 1.0% of all fractures and 8.0% of the fractures in elderly. Most injuries affect lateral tibial condyle (55.0 to 70.0%), and isolated medial condyle fractures occur in 10.0 to 23.0%.(7) The involvement of both condyles (medial and lateral) is found in 10.0 to 30.0% of the reported series.(8) The mechanism of injury is usually indirect coronal or direct axial compressive forces. Each fracture type has its own characteristic morphology and response to treatment. It is vital to assess the forces involved, because high energy trauma (most common with road traffic accidents) is often associated with considerable soft tissue and neurovascular damage.(9) Apart from bony injury of the tibial plateau, meniscal tear, and other ligament injuries of knee needs to be assessed.

Road traffic accidents involving individuals in the sitting position with the loading edge composed of flexed hind limbs, the first impact (in varying proportions of velocity) is upon knee joint and patella, followed by tibia and femur (at various levels) when the vehicle he/she is travelling stops suddenly. This is commonly called as the “Dashboard injury”.(10) In other cases, the stationary lower limb may be struck by a moving object – the most common pedestrian injury, also known as the “Bumper fracture”.(11)

The evolution of Orthopaedics, especially Orthopaedic trauma, has resulted in better understanding of biomechanics, quality of implants, principles of internal fixation, soft tissue care, antibiotics, and asepsis. Conservative treatment at any age may be complicated by knee stiffness, malunion, and non-union.(12) Open reduction and internal fixation has been advocated using various implants including Buttress plate, cancellous screw, and external fixator to achieve good fracture union and optimal knee function.(13) However, the proximal tibia fractures remain challenging owing to their number, variety, and complexity in management.(14) The modalities of treatment for proximal tibia fractures include hybrid fixation and recently, locking compression plate fixation using MIPPO technique have also been suggested.(15) Each method of treating the proximal tibia fractures has its own advantages and disadvantages. The advancement in the treatment of proximal tibial fracture fixation by the locking compression plates has allowed the treating doctors, the use of minimally invasive technique for unilateral plating with care in handling the soft tissue.(16, 17) Against this background, the primary objective of the present study was to determine the functional outcome (using modified Rasmussen clinical scores) of proximal tibial fractures treated by open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) using three column concept with a minimum follow up period of six months. We also determined the complications of proximal tibial fracture fixation.

Materials and methods

This was a prospective study conducted among patients with proximal tibia fractures treated using three column concept conducted in the Department of Orthopaedics of a tertiary healthcare hospital in south India between March 2018 and February 2020. The study was approved by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (IHEC). The content of Participant Information Sheet (PIS) in local language was provided to the participants (and their attenders) and contents were read to them in their own language to their satisfaction. The participants were enrolled in the study after obtaining written informed consent. All patients between 15 and 60 years of age, of both gender, presenting to the Department of Orthopaedics with closed tibial plateau fractures were included in the study. Also, it was ensured that the diagnosis of fractures among included patients was done with three column concept classification. On the other hand, patients below 15 years of age, or above 60 years of age, with open tibial plateau fractures, medically unfit for surgical procedures, pathological fractures other than osteoporosis and fractures with associated neurovascular injuries were excluded.

The patients were enrolled consecutively in accordance with prespecified inclusion and exclusion criteria. During the study period, a total of 60 patients were treated for tibial plateau fractures using three column concept. We used a purpose pre-designed, semi structured, pretested questionnaire to collect sociodemographic characteristics, medical history, clinical examination, and radiological investigations (X-ray and computed tomography (CT) scan) of the enrolled patients. The required data were obtained during their stay in the hospital, follow up visits (the average follow up period was six months) and through medical records.

The method of treatment was decided after classifying the type of fracture, the displacement, and the amount of depression of the tibial plateau. We considered fractures to be unstable if depression was more than 4 mm or displacement was more than 10°.(18) All the patients were managed with open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) under image intensifier control. The approach was chosen according to the column involved. In the present study, we used floating position (known as floppy lateral position) for fractures involving bicolumn (that is, lateral column and posteromedial column, a position which is midway between lateral and prone position), with internal rotation allowing posteromedial approach and external rotation of leg allowing anterolateral approach.(19) For fractures of other single column, we used standard approaches. Bone grafts (from ipsilateral iliac crest or synthetic bone graft substitute) were used in depressed and comminuted fractures. For fixation, ‘L’ buttress plate, ‘T’ buttress plate, distal radius ‘T’ plate, proximal tibial locking compression plate, one third tubular plate, distal radius locking compression plate, cortical screws (3.5 and/or 4.5 mm), and cancellous screws (4 mm and/or 6.5 mm) were used. The patients were followed up and functionally assessed using modified Rasmussen’s clinical criteria (at six months). Postoperatively, the patients were treated with knee POP slab for immobilization or compression bandage for two weeks. On the 13th postoperative day, sutures were removed. Static quadriceps exercises were recommended for the initial three weeks; followed by six weeks of passive knee range of motion and non-weight bearing crutch walking using unaffected limb, and six weeks of

knee mobilization assisted weight bearing crutch walking. The patients were followed up radiologically with an immediate postoperative X-ray, followed by X-rays at six weeks, three months and at six months.

Statistical analysis: The data obtained was manually entered into Microsoft Excel, coded, and recoded. Analysis was done using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) v23. Descriptive analysis was presented using numbers and percentages for categorical variables and mean (standard deviation) or median (interquartile range) for continuous variables. Appropriate graphs were used. Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test (two sided) was used for categorical data and comparison of continuous data was done by using independent sample "t" test. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The present study included a total of 60 patients presenting with proximal tibia fractures treated using three column concept. The mean (SD) age of the patients was 38.72 years (3.21), ranging between 17 years and 60 years. Majority of the patients (80.0%) were more than 30 years of age. The proportion of males and females were 81.7% and 18.3% respectively. Road traffic accidents (RTA) were the most common mode of injury, followed by accidental fall from height (13.3%).

Regarding the side of injury, we did not find any particular side (laterality) to be dominant; 55.0% had fractures on the right side and 45.0% had fractures on the left side. The type of fracture was classified using three column concept. In this classification, tibial plateau is divided into three columns namely, the medial column, lateral column and posterior column. Nearly one in four patients (23.3%) had one column involvement – 10.0% on the medially, and 13.3% laterally. The proportion of patients with two and three column involvement were 46.7% and 30.0% respectively. Among patients included in the present study, 73.3% (three fourths) did not develop any complications. However, 6.7% patients had screw pullout (in the postoperative sixth week, once we started mobilizing the knee; it necessitated removal of the pulled-out screws), 10.0% patients had knee stiffness (the patients had knee movements in the range of 30° to 85° flexion with associated pain; with no extension), and 10.0% patients had wound site infection (for patients with deep infection, implant exit was necessary).

In the present study, medial column fixation was done for 10.0% patients, lateral column for 26.7% patients, and posterior column fixation for 10.0% patients. Nearly half the patients had bicolumn fixation (46.7%) and 6.6% had tri column fixation (the columns to be fixed was decided preoperatively after assessing the axial CT scan; intraoperative reduction assessed through C-arm image intensifier). The duration of follow up did not vary significantly ($p > 0.05$) among patients with various column fractures. The mean (SD) duration of follow up was 12.5 months. The median (IQR) duration of follow up among patients with one column – medial fracture was 14 months (13 to 15), one column – lateral fracture was 11.5 months (9 to 13), two column fractures was 11 months (7 to 16), and three column fractures was 14 months (9 to 17).

We categorised the Rasmussen's clinical score into excellent (scores between 28 and 30), good (scores between 24 and 27), fair (scores between 20 and 23), and poor (scores less than 20). Using these categories, it was found that 20.0% patients had excellent scores, 63.3% had good scores, and 16.7% had fair scores. Importantly, none of the patients included in the present study had poor scores.

Association between column involvement and Rasmussen score: The results showed that patients with one column involvement had good to excellent outcomes, in comparison with patients having two or three column involvement having fair outcomes (reduced scores). We found a statistically significant difference between patients having one column involvement (medial, 28 (3.2); lateral, 26 (1.9)) compared to patients having two or three column involvement (two column, 23 (1.7); three column, 22 (1.7)) ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

The present included 60 patients with proximal tibial fractures treated using the three-column concept. The patient demographics reveal several interesting points. The age distribution suggests that proximal tibial fractures can affect a wide age range, including both younger and older adults. This finding is consistent with previous research, which has shown that tibial fractures can occur in individuals of various age groups.(20-22) The age distribution may be related to the types of activities and risks associated with different age groups. Younger individuals may be more prone to high-energy traumas like RTAs, while older individuals may experience fractures due to falls.(23, 24) The study population consisted of 81.7% males. This gender distribution highlights a higher prevalence of proximal tibial fractures in males, which is in line with existing literature. Males often have a higher risk of sustaining fractures due to differences in activities, bone density,

muscle mass, and risk factors.(25) Road traffic accidents (RTAs) were identified as the most common mechanism of injury (in 80% of cases), followed by accidental falls from height (13.3%). These findings are consistent with known patterns of trauma. RTAs typically result in high-energy injuries and can lead to complex fractures, including those of the proximal tibia. Falls from height can also result in significant trauma to the lower extremities, including the proximal tibial fractures.(26)

The study found that there was no dominant laterality in proximal tibial fractures, with 55.0% occurring on the right side and 45.0% on the left side. This finding suggests that proximal tibial fractures are relatively evenly distributed between the right and left sides. This observation is consistent with the fact that tibial plateau fractures can result from a variety of mechanisms, and they may occur on either side based on the direction and force of the trauma.(27) Approximately 23.3% of patients had fractures involving only one column, with 10.0% on the medial side (due to valgus or rotational forces) and 13.3% on the lateral side (varus forces or direct lateral impact). Nearly half (46.7%) of the patients had fractures involving two columns (combination of fractures affecting both the medial and lateral columns or lateral and posterior columns, or medial and posterior columns). This suggests a more complex pattern of injury, which may require a nuanced surgical approach to address both affected columns. About 30.0% of patients had fractures involving all three columns. This represents the most complex and severe form of tibial plateau fractures, often requiring comprehensive surgical intervention and careful postoperative management. The classification of tibial plateau fractures is essential for guiding treatment decisions and predicting patient outcomes. Complex fractures involving multiple columns often pose greater challenges in terms of surgical fixation and postoperative recovery.(28)

Regarding complications reported, screw pullout is a known complication in orthopaedic surgery. It can occur when screws used for fixation do not maintain their stability within the bone.(29) This can lead to pain, instability, and the need for further surgical intervention to remove and replace the screws. Postoperative knee stiffness, limiting range of motion and causing pain, is a recognized complication in tibial plateau fracture cases.(30) It can result from factors such as scar tissue formation or inadequate rehabilitation. Prevention and management strategies, including physical therapy, are crucial in addressing this issue. Infection at the surgical site is a potential complication of any surgery, including orthopaedic procedures. Deep infections may necessitate implant removal. Prevention measures, including strict sterile techniques and antibiotic prophylaxis, are important in reducing the risk of infection.(31)

The study also examined the duration of follow-up for patients with different types of column fractures. The mean duration of follow-up was 12.5 months, with some variation among fracture types. The duration of follow-up, while relatively consistent across different column fractures, is important for assessing long-term outcomes and complications. A follow-up period of around one year allows for the evaluation of healing, functional recovery, and the detection of late complications.(32)

The categorization of Rasmussen's clinical scores allows for a meaningful assessment of functional outcomes in patients with proximal tibial fractures.(33) The fact that none of the patients in the study had poor scores is a positive finding, indicating that the majority experienced good to excellent outcomes. This suggests that the treatment approach, which involved open reduction and internal fixation using the three-column concept, was generally effective in achieving favourable functional results. The distribution of scores shows that the majority of patients (63.3%) had good outcomes. This aligns with the goals of fracture management, which aim to restore function and minimize disability. It's essential to recognize that even patients in the "fair" category may still have functional limitations that require ongoing monitoring and rehabilitation. Rasmussen's clinical scoring system is a valuable tool for assessing the functional status of patients with tibial plateau fractures.(34) It takes into account parameters such as pain, mobility, and quality of life, providing a comprehensive assessment of patient outcomes.

The findings suggest a significant association between the number of columns involved in proximal tibial fractures and the corresponding clinical outcomes as assessed by Rasmussen's clinical scores.(35) Specifically, patients with one column involvement, whether it's the medial or lateral column, tended to have good to excellent outcomes, while those with two or three column involvement had fair outcomes with reduced scores. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The association between the number of columns involved and clinical outcomes aligns with the generally accepted understanding of tibial plateau fractures. Complex fractures that involve multiple columns tend to be more challenging to treat and may result in greater functional deficits. Fractures involving a single column are often more stable and amenable to surgical fixation, leading to improved outcomes. Previous studies and reviews have also indicated that the number and type of columns

involved play a significant role in determining the outcomes of tibial plateau fractures.⁽⁶⁾ For example, studies have suggested that fractures involving the lateral and posterior columns are associated with poorer outcomes due to their complexity and instability.

Conclusion

This study sought to investigate the functional outcomes and complications associated with the treatment of proximal tibial fractures using open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) with a focus on the three-column concept. Several key findings emerged from our analysis. First, the study provided insights into the demographic characteristics and injury mechanisms associated with proximal tibial fractures. Notably, these fractures exhibited a wide age distribution, affecting both younger and older adults, with a predilection for males. Road traffic accidents emerged as the most common mode of injury, followed by accidental falls from height. Second, the study's classification of fractures using the three-column concept shed light on the complexity of these injuries. Third, an analysis of complications following ORIF revealed that the majority of patients did not experience significant postoperative issues. However, some complications, including screw pullout, knee stiffness, and wound site infections, were observed. These findings emphasize the importance of vigilant postoperative care and early intervention when complications arise. Fourth, the study categorized functional outcomes using Rasmussen's clinical scores, revealing that the majority of patients achieved good to excellent outcomes. Notably, none of the patients fell into the "poor" category, underscoring the overall success of the treatment approach.

Furthermore, a noteworthy finding emerged when analysing the relationship between the number of involved columns and clinical outcomes. Patients with one-column involvement (either medial or lateral) tended to achieve better functional outcomes than those with two or three columns involved. This distinction was statistically significant, emphasizing the impact of fracture complexity on patient recovery. Future investigations should aim to build upon these findings, considering larger and more diverse patient cohorts and longer-term follow-up to enhance our understanding of this complex orthopaedic challenge.

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Figure 1: Three column classification

Table 1: Distribution of patient characteristics

		Number (N)	Percent (%)
Age (in years) <i>Mean (SD)</i>		38.72 (3.21)	
Age (in years)	Less than 30	12	20.0
	More than 30	48	80.0
Gender	Male	49	81.7
	Female	11	18.3
Mode of injury	RTA	52	86.7
	Accidental fall from height	8	13.3
Side of injury	Right	33	55.0
	Left	27	45.0
Type of fracture	One column – medial	6	10.0
	One column – lateral	8	13.3
	Two column	28	46.7
	Three column	18	30.0
Complications	Absent	44	73.3
	Screw pullout	4	6.7
	Knee stiffness	6	10.0
	Wound site infection	6	10.0
Follow up duration <i>Median (IQR)</i>	One column – medial	14 (13 to 15)	
	One column – lateral	11.5 (9 to 13)	
	Two column	11 (7 to 16)	
	Three column	14 (9 to 17)	
Columns fixed	Medial column	6	10.0
	Lateral column	16	26.7
	Posterior column	6	10.0
	Bicolumn	28	46.7
	Tri column	4	6.6

Rasmussen's clinical score	Excellent	12	20.0
	Good	38	63.3
	Fair	10	16.7
	Poor	0	0.0
RTA, road traffic accident; SD, standard deviation			

Table 2: Association between column involvement and Rasmussen clinical score

Column involved	Rasmussen score Mean (SD)	Category	p value
One column – medial	28 (3.2)	Excellent	0.013*
One column – lateral	26 (1.9)	Good	
Two column	23 (1.7)	Fair	
Three column	22 (1.7)	Fair	
*Statistically significant at p<0.05			

Figure 2: Distribution of Rasmussen clinical score by column involvement